

The Origins of Equilibrium Price Theory: a Critical Survey from a Temporal Perspective

Kanade Kubota

Abstract

Conventional market equilibrium theory relies on the basic assumption that the market prices are determined at the intersection of supply and demand curves, regardless of the kinds of traded goods. However, the author's previous work demonstrated that this premise does not hold in money-mediated markets, even under mathematically idealized conditions; instead, such markets equilibrate at prices deviated from the intersection. The present paper aims to identify the cause of this contradiction by tracing the historical development of market equilibrium theory. More specifically, we analyze the arguments of representative proponents in each era—from the Smith's proposal of natural price to the Debreu's formalization of general equilibrium model—and compare and classify them from several aspects such as temporality, kind of goods, and terminology. As a result, our analysis reveals a logical inconsistencies in the claims that money-mediated market will move its price toward the equilibrium point which are asserted by Marshall and Samuelson's textbooks. These inconsistencies appear to originate from Marshall's attempt to incorporate the works by Jevons and Walras into the classical economic framework, despite the fact that their static methodology is not applicable to a dynamic and continuous-time model. Consequently, the traditional premise that prices are determined at the intersection of two curves are not logically sustained in case of money-mediated markets. Our analysis not only calls into question the basic understanding of market behavior but also suggests the need for a fundamental reconstruction of economic theory.

Keywords: Market Equilibrium Theory, Disequilibrium Market, Marginal Revolution.

1 Introduction

Market equilibrium theory has long been accepted as a fundamental principle of economics. Nevertheless, we can observe many markets in a disequilibrium state in the real economy. Various explanations have been proposed to account for the inconsistency between the theory and reality. Keynes, for instance, explained the existence of involuntary unemployment by arguing that Say's law does not generally hold (Keynes 1936). New Keynesian economists typically assume price rigidity caused by menu cost and information asymmetries to incorporate disequilibrium markets into their models (Mankiw 1985; Akerlof 1970). In addition, Robinson and Chamberlin argued that markets are prevented from reaching equilibrium due to the oligopolistic or monopolistic nature of firms (Robinson 1956 [1933]; Chamberlain 1966 [1962]). While some of these scholars were strongly critical of market equilibrium theory, they did not reject its core propositions.

However, the author's mathematical analysis of market exchange obtained a different result from conventional thought even under idealized conditions (Kubota 2026). In this paper (hereafter referred to as 'DTV paper'),¹ the analysis assumes bounded rationality of economic agents over an open time horizon and explicitly considers the temporal continuity of

¹In (Kubota 2026), a new value theory—the Dynamic Theory of Value (DTV)—is proposed, which incorporates the temporal continuity of exchanges. "DTV" is used as an abbreviation for this theory.

exchanges. As a result, it is demonstrated that barter markets will reach an equilibrium at the intersection of supply and demand curves, that is compatible to the conventional theory (Figure 1a). Conversely, money-mediated markets are shown to reach an equilibrium point away from the intersection of the two curves because of the asymmetric nature of money and commodities. The markets consequently converge to an asymmetric state in which producers adjust their outputs in accordance with demand level (Figure 1b).² In conventional theory, prices are determined at the "equilibrium" point (i.e., the intersection of two curves) regardless of the type of goods exchanged, resulting in a clear inconsistency with our analysis.

Figure 1: Equilibrium state presented in the DTV paper

The findings of the DTV paper provide a new explanation for the gap between the theory and reality. However, given that the market mechanism has been the main interest of economics for centuries, the assertion that such a fundamental flaw has only recently been identified is unlikely to be readily accepted. The present paper aims to resolve this concern by analyzing the historical development of the theory and by critically assessing its underlying foundation.

2 Origins and History of the Equilibrium Price Theory

Contemporary introductory textbooks of economics, including Mankiw's famous ones, typically offer a uniform and informal explanations of market equilibrium theory without citing primary sources. In later stages of the curriculum, students learn general equilibrium theory based on sophisticated mathematics. Because of its advanced specialization, many students achieve only a partial understanding of the theory. Nevertheless, its mathematical difficulty is often interpreted as evidence of rigor and validity, resulting in a wide acceptance with authority. Furthermore, these mathematical contributions are frequently

²The DTV paper argues that prices converge to production cost plus a markup rather than to the intersection of demand and supply. While similar claims can be found in traditional Post-Keynesian theories of pricing, their arguments are primarily based on observations of firm behavior. The novelty of the DTV paper lies in its derivation of an "disequilibrium" market theory from mathematically idealized assumptions.

associated with Adam Smith's famous metaphor of the *invisible hand*, thereby conveying the impression that the market equilibrium theory has been inherited within the tradition of economics for centuries, and thus requires no further critical assessment. Such a situation generates a mystification of the market equilibrium theory and impose a significant psychological burden on those who attempt to criticize it.

However, the historical development of market equilibrium theory differs considerably from what is suggested by contemporary standard economics education. In fact, the market theory has undergone substantial evolution from the era of Adam Smith to the present day, accompanied with various thoughts and controversies. Moreover, many of early arguments lacked rigor, and some are still present without solid foundation. To illustrate these, this section traces the historical development of the market equilibrium theory by examining the arguments of the key proponents in each era.³

2.1 Adam Smith

Adam Smith (1723-1790) was a British philosopher of the eighteenth century and is widely regarded as the founder of classical economics. Nowadays, his famous phrase "the invisible hand" is frequently cited in the context of market liberalism. However, somewhat surprisingly, the market theory he developed in *The Wealth of Nations* differs in many respects from modern market theory (Smith 1904 [1776]).⁴

Smith explained the mechanism of market price determination as follows (Smith 1904 [1776], Book I, Ch. 7, pp. 73-75). He first introduced the concept of the *natural price*, defined as an idealized price that abstracts temporary fluctuations from the actual market price and is calculated at the prevailing rates of production elements, such as rent, wages and profit. Market price is determined by the balance between the quantity of a commodity which is actually brought to market and effectual demand, where effectual demand denotes the demand of those who are willing to pay the natural price.⁵ The adjustment mechanism of commodity supply and market prices works as follows:

- When the quantity of a commodity on sale exceeds the effectual demand, a shortage of buyers provoke a competition among sellers, driving the market price below the

³The title of the present paper may suggest to some readers a comprehensive description of the history of economic thought. This section, however, does not aim to provide an exhaustive survey of the development of economic thought. Instead, it seeks to extract and summarize the key issues necessary for investigating the cause of the inconsistency raised by the DTV paper. Accordingly, it should be noted that the arguments of other major proponents—such as Cournot, Menger and Pareto—as well as many important perspectives, are not present in the following discussion.

⁴In contemporary debates, Smith's arguments are not understood accurately and are frequently presented in a distorted manner. In fact, the phrase "the invisible hand" appears only once in *The Wealth of Nations* and is not used in the context of market theory, but rather in a critique of mercantilist policy. In other words, Smith's intension was not to celebrate the autonomous functioning of markets, but rather to emphasize that unnecessary intervention by the government will distort the appropriate distribution of resources.

⁵Smith defined the term "demand" broadly as the total desire for a commodity, including that of individuals who are unwilling to pay its natural price. Thus, he defined a narrower sense of demand as *effectual demand*—restricted by a willingness to pay—to make distinction from the broader notion of demand.

natural price. Lower profitability then induces some producers to withdraw from production of that commodity. The resulting decrease in output causes the market price to rise toward the natural price.

- When the quantity of a commodity on sale falls below the effectual demand, a shortage of supply provoke a competition among buyers, driving the market price above the natural price. Higher profitability then attracts new producers for that commodity. The resulting increase in output causes the market price to decline toward the natural price.
- When the quantity of a commodity on sale equals the effectual demand, the market price coincides with the natural price. At this point, producers are exactly satisfied with the current profitability, which causes no adjustment in output and market price.

As such, market price of commodity is always gravitated toward its natural price. Ideally, it is most efficient for the producers to make supply amount consistent with effectual demand at any moment. In practice, however, the producers are unable to predict future so that such equality is always met because effectual demand and supply fluctuates continuously. Therefore, the market price never fully converges to the natural price but instead fluctuates around it (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Natural price and actual price over time

By interpreting the quantity of a commodity on sale as "supply" and effectual demand as "demand", the preceding argument can be broadly regarded as a theory of supply and demand equilibrium. Yet Smith did not offer a quantitative formulation of the level of market prices, and thus his analysis remained essentially qualitative.

2.2 John S. Mill

Principles of Political Economy, written by John Stuart Mill (1806-1873), was considered as a representative textbook of political economy before the marginal revolution (Mill 1909 [1848]). Mill's explanation of market price determination builds upon Smith's arguments and is organized into two temporal perspectives, the short run and the long run.

In the short run, the adjustment process caused by discrepancies between supply and demand plays a dominant role in determination of market prices (Mill 1909 [1848], III.2.§§3-4, pp. 320-322). Here, supply denotes "the quantity offered for sale," whereas demand

represents “*the wish to possess, combined with the power of purchasing,*” namely, the quantity demanded at a given price. His notion of demand resembles to Smith’s notion of “effectual demand”, a term also appears in Mill’s work. However, while Smith associates effectual demand exclusively with the willingness to pay at the natural price, Mill adopts a more general definition by treating effectual demand as a function of price. The equilibrium mechanism between supply and demand is described as follows (Mill 1909 [1848], III.2.§4, pp. 321-322):

- When demand exceeds supply, competition arises among buyers, resulting in an increase in the market price.
- When demand falls short of supply, competition arises among sellers, resulting in a decrease in the market price.

As a consequence of these mechanism, the price adjustments continues until supply equals demand. Compared with Smith, Mill’s discussion is more quantitative, as he introduced a concept of demand function and argued that prices are determined at the level where demand equals supply. This can be illustrated by using a modern supply-demand diagram as shown in Figure 3. The price is determined at the intersection of supply and demand curves, as in modern equilibrium theory. Yet supply curve is represented as a vertical line, as supply is constant by definition.

Figure 3: Mechanism of market equilibrium by Mill

In the long run, adjustments of supply induced by capital mobility become more dominant (Mill 1909 [1848], I.7.§§1-2, pp. 324-327). Given the condition of sustainable production, the price of commodity is required to cover the production costs as well as sufficient profit. Over time, the rate of profit on capital—more precisely, its expected rate—tends to be equalized across various types of commodities. This is because differences of profit rates are attenuated as capitalists reallocate their capital in pursuit of higher returns. On this basis, Mill described the adjustment process associated with capital mobility as follows:

- When supply persistently falls short of demand, the commodity can be sold at prices exceeding its natural price, resulting in a rate of profit above the average level.

Consequently, capital inflows occur, leading to an increase in supply.

- When supply persistently exceeds demand, the commodity can be sold only at prices below its natural price, resulting in a rate of profit below the average level. Consequently, capital outflows occur, leading to a decrease in supply.

As a result of these adjustment mechanisms, temporary divergence between supply and demand does not persist. Therefore, when averaged over sufficiently long span, supply and demand coincides, and the market price converges to the natural price. This argument is essentially the same to Smith's claim that the market price is gravitated toward the natural price (Figure 2).

Mill further advances his argument that leads to the labor theory of value. Since profit rates converge to the average level in the long run, the rate of profit shared in the price will be equalized among commodities. By necessity, the similar equalization occurs in terms of the rate of production costs shared in the price. As production costs are largely proportional to the amount of labor embodied, market prices likewise tend to be proportional to labor embodied in the long run. Taken together, Mill concluded that a stable market equilibrium is achieved when commodities are exchanged in proportion to their production costs, or at ratios corresponding to their natural prices.

According to Mill, the above argument applies equally to barter and to trade mediated by money. In either case, the laws of value hold—temporary market prices are governed by supply and demand, whereas long-run market prices are determined by production costs. It follows that the essential relationship among goods, such as exchange ratio, is maintained by the introduction of money:

There cannot, in short, be intrinsically a more insignificant thing, in the economy of society, than money; except in the character of a contrivance for sparing time and labour. It is a machine for doing quickly and commodiously, what would be done, though less quickly and commodiously, without it: and like many other kinds of machinery, it only exerts a distinct and independent influence of its own when it gets out of order.

The introduction of money does not interfere with the operation of any of the Laws of Value laid down in the preceding chapters. The reasons which make the temporary or market value of things depend on the demand and supply, and their average and permanent values upon their cost of production, are as applicable to a money system as to a system of barter. Things which by barter would exchange for one another, will, if sold for money, sell for an equal amount of it, and so will exchange for one another still, though the process of exchanging them will consist of two operations instead of only one. The relations of commodities to one another remain unaltered by money: the only new relation introduced is their relation to money itself; how much or how little money they will exchange for; in other words, how the Exchange Value of money itself is determined. (Mill 1909 [1848], III.7§3, p. 351)

His assertion is known today as the *veil of money* view. Although such a stance that does not acknowledge essential role of money was later criticized by Keynes, there was little controversies on this issue in Mill's era.

2.3 William S. Jevons

William Stanley Jevons (1835-1882) is widely known as a prominent of marginal utility theory, together with Carl Menger. Although mathematical approaches had existed prior to the marginal revolution, the political economy was still regarded as a moral science in his era, and there remained strong resistance to the mathematization of economics. In this context, Jevons pursued a mathematical formalization of market exchange theory (Jevons 1888).

The novelty of Jevons's approach lies in the rigorous formalization of economic behavior through the introduction of utility-maximization approach and the law of diminishing marginal utility. An overview of his analysis is as follows. He considered a single barter market in which two types of commodities, A and B , are traded. There are two groups of agents, X and Y , where X are initially endowed only with commodity A , while Y are initially endowed only with commodity B . The exchange ratio is temporarily assumed to be fixed at some given value. At the initial stage, both groups of agents, X and Y , engage in trading because, from either perspective, the marginal utility of commodity obtained exceeds that of commodity relinquished in a single transaction. As trading continues, diminishing marginal utility implies that the marginal utility obtained falls, while the marginal utility lost rises. Eventually, a point is reached at which either X or Y finds that further transactions are no longer beneficial and ceases trading (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Marginal utility (MU) of commodities

Recall that we have chosen the exchange ratio arbitrarily. Accordingly, the amounts of transactions desired by X and Y do not necessarily coincide. When such a mismatch occurs, the exchange ratio adjusts through the mechanism described below (see Figure 5):

- If X wishes more transactions than Y , some agents in X are left unmatched. To achieve their desired amount, they therefore accept a less favorable exchange ratio, which lowers X 's desired transaction amount and raises that of Y .

- If X wishes less transactions than Y , some agents in Y are left unmatched. To achieve their desired amount, they therefore accept a less favorable exchange ratio, which raises X 's desired transaction amount and lowers that of Y .
- This adjustment proceeds until the desired transaction amounts of both groups coincide.

Once the adjustment process is complete, all agents face equal marginal utilities for the commodities exchanged— A and B —in a single transaction, and the exchange ratio coincides with the ratio of their marginal utilities.

Figure 5: Mechanism of market equilibrium by Jevons

On the basis of these findings, Jevons argued that the notion of value, in the sense of “*esteem or desirableness*” that individuals attach to commodities, originates in marginal utility. He therefore rejected the traditional labor theory of value—which regards labor as the source of value—by pointing to the existence of exchange value in commodities not produced by labor as a counterexample. (Jevons 1888, Ch. 4, “The Origin of Value,” pp. 119-120).

2.4 Léon Walras

Léon Walras (1834-1910) is widely known as the founder of the general equilibrium theory, which treats multi-market exchanges (Walras 1983 [1874]). Like Jevons, Walras independently derived the same idea that the exchange ratio equals the ratio of marginal utilities almost contemporaneously—which he described as the “theorem of maximum satisfaction” (Walras 1983 [1874], §80). A key difference from Jevons is that Walras derived supply and demand functions from utility theory and incorporated them into the conventional framework of supply and demand equilibrium.

Walras’s formalization rests on the assumption that supply and demand are simultaneously cleared across multiple markets by a price-determining mechanism analogous to a stock-exchange auction (Walras 1983 [1874], §42). Under such hypothetical markets, the price adjustment process functions as follows:

- When effective demand exceeds effective supply at a given price, some buyers are

unable to find counterparts. In this case, the auctioneer who have received buy orders at prices higher than the current one bid up the market price.

- When effective supply exceeds effective demand at a given price, some sellers are unable to find counterparts. In this case, the auctioneer who have received sell orders at prices lower than the current one bid down the market price.
- The above adjustment process (commonly called *tâtonnement*) is repeated until effective demand and effective supply coincide. Once this condition is satisfied in all markets, prices are determined and transactions are carried out simultaneously.

Following Mill's definition, effective demand denotes the quantity desired to purchase at a given price. In addition, a new term "effective supply" ("*effective offer*" in original) was introduced as its counterpart, representing the quantity desired to supply at a given price.⁶

Such a price adjustment mechanism clearly departs from real-world markets and has long been criticized as unrealistic. However, Walras countered by criticizing conventional theories for their lack of generality, arguing that they focus only on specific cases such as money-mediated exchange and reproducible goods. He maintained that, for the development of core theory, one should not begin with such a specific model but instead with a more general, mathematically pure construction—namely, the model of the perfectly competitive market (Walras 1983 [1874], §43).

2.5 Alfred Marshall

Principles of Economics, written by Alfred Marshall (1842-1924), was a representative economics textbook in the early twentieth century (Marshall 1920). Owing to its exposition of supply and demand equilibrium based on marginal utility theory, Marshall is often regarded as the founder of neoclassical economics who unified the ideas emerging from the marginal revolution. Nevertheless, a closer examination reveals several differences between Marshall and other marginalists.

Like Walras, Marshall defined both demand and supply as concepts dependent on price. However, his representation differs in that the functional relationship—argument and output—is inverted. More precisely, Marshall defined the *demand price* as the price at which consumers are willing to purchase a given quantity of commodity (Marshall 1920, III.3.§2, p. 62). Likewise, the *supply price* is defined as the price at which producers are willing to offer a given quantity for sale (Marshall 1920, IV.1.§2, p. 86). Such an inverted representation is peculiar to Marshall and seems to originate from his adoption of cardinal utility. Under this approach, utility is quantified by expressing the satisfaction derived from commodities and money in terms of the amount of money an individual is willing to pay to acquire them (Marshall 1920, III.6.§§1-3, pp. 78-80).

⁶Prior to Walras's work, the prefix "effective" was commonly added to emphasize that these quantities are functions of price. However, this prefix was gradually dropped, and they came to be simply called "supply" and "demand". Although the term "effective demand" still appear in modern economics—particularly in the context of Keynesian economics—its meaning and nuance differ from the original.

In contrast to Jevons and Walras, who first focused on hypothetical market models in pursuit of rigorous formalization, Marshall adopted a more practical approach and analyzed realistic markets in which commodities are exchanged by money. He described the mechanism of price adjustment as follows (Marshall 1920, V.3.§6, p. 201):

- When the demand price exceeds the supply price, producers are able to sell their products at a price sufficient to justify the current level of output, and therefore increase the quantity supplied.
- When the demand price falls below the supply price, producer are unable to sell their products at a price sufficient to justify the current level of output, and therefore reduce the quantity supplied.
- These price adjustments function so as to move the market toward the equilibrium point at which the supply price and the demand price coincide, much as a pendulum is drawn toward its central position by gravity.

The above price mechanism can be illustrated by the so-called Marshallian cross, a diagram that depicts demand and supply prices as functions of the quantity exchanged (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Mechanism of market equilibrium by Marshall

Unlike Jevons, who rejected the labor theory of value and developed the utility theory of value, Marshall sought to integrate the two. Following Mill, he analyzed market behavior from both short run and long run perspectives. In general, changes in costs of production take longer to exert their influence than changes in demand. Accordingly, in the short run, the utility theory of value—emphasizing demand-side factors—plays the dominant role in price-determination, whereas in the long run, the labor theory of value—emphasizing supply-side factors—becomes more prominent.⁷

Marshall prioritized practicality over mathematical rigor, and was especially concerned with the dynamic aspects of the economy. However, since the formalization of a dynamic

⁷This argument is famously known as the "scissors analogy." Marshall remarked that "We might as reasonably dispute whether it is the upper or the under blade of a pair of scissors that cuts a piece of paper, as whether value is governed by utility or cost of production." (Marshall 1920, V.3.§7, pp. 203).

economic system remains subject to technical difficulties even today, his analysis is less rigorous than those of Jevons and Walras. Marshall acknowledged that the time element constitutes the greatest difficulty in economic analysis and stressed the limitations of available methodologies in his era. For this reason, he argued that economists should rely not only on mathematical analysis but also on common sense and intuition (Marshall 1920, V.5.§2, p. 215).

2.6 Paul Samuelson

Economics, written by Paul Samuelson (1915-2009), became the standard textbook throughout the latter half of the twentieth century, replacing Marshall's *Principles of Economics*. His exposition of market equilibrium theory is substantially identical to Marshall's, but differs in its descriptive manner (Samuelson 1997 [1948], pp. 447–457).

The demand and supply are defined as follows:

The demand schedule related to prices and the amounts people wish to buy. *By the supply schedule, we naturally mean the relation between prices and the amounts that people are willing to produce and sell.* (Samuelson 1997 [1948], p. 455) (italics in original)

Here, "amounts" are defined per unit of time. Prices are specified in dollars, suggesting that money-mediated exchange is considered. These definitions differ from Marshall's in that the functions take price, rather than quantity, as their argument. This change is to reflect the influence of Walrasian general equilibrium analysis.

Similarly, Samuelson's explanation of price-determination differs from that of Marshall in its description. In contrast to Marshall, who focused on price, Samuelson explained the price adjustment process through inventory imbalances:⁸

- When supply exceeds demand, inventories continue to accumulate. This induces competition among sellers seeking to reduce excess stocks, leading to a decline in price.
- When demand exceeds supply, inventories continue to shrink. At some point, producers become unable to supply a sufficient quantity to all willing buyers, leading to a rise in price driven by pressure from disappointed consumers.

Samuelson illustrated the above price-adjustment mechanism using the familiar supply-demand diagram (Figure 7). Notably, his diagram places quantity on the horizontal axis

⁸It is stated that: "At \$1.40, the producers will be bringing 130 (million) bushels to the market every month [see Col. (3)]. But the amount demanded by consumers will be only 52 (million) bushels per month [see Col. (2)]. As stocks of wheat begin to pile up, competitive sellers will cut the price just a little. [...] For a comparison of Cols. (2) and (3) shows that consumption will exceed production *at that price*. Storehouses will begin to be emptied; disappointed demanders who cannot get wheat will tend to bid the price up." (italics in original) (Samuelson 1997 [1948], p. 456)

and price on the vertical axis, as in Marshall's diagram. Although the graphical representation of a function usually assigns its argument to the horizontal axis, Samuelson's textbook reverses the horizontal and vertical axes relative to this convention, which makes the diagram consistent with Marshall's in direction. This observation suggests that Samuelson was likely drawing on Marshall's textbook, despite the absence of explicit citation.

Figure 7: Mechanism of market equilibrium by Samuelson

Since the 1980s, curriculum of economics courses at universities has become increasingly standardized. As a consequence, recent introductory economics textbooks share similar content, with many of them modeled on Samuelson's textbook. There are few differences among these textbooks in their explanations of market equilibrium—the claim that prices are determined at the intersection of supply and demand curves—largely because Samuelson's exposition has been repeatedly reproduced.

2.7 Gérard Debreu

General equilibrium theory, proposed by Walras, solves an enormous system of equations to derive a set of prices that equilibrates all markets at once. The existence of a positive real solution to such a system was not self-evident and remained unsolved for many years. A mathematical resolution was provided by the French mathematician Gérard Debreu (1921-2004), who rigorously proved the existence of an equilibrium solution under certain assumptions, thereby establishing a formal mathematical foundation for general equilibrium theory (Debreu 1959). The model he developed is referred to as the Arrow–Debreu model.

In (Debreu 1959), while the analysis centers on establishing the existence of equilibrium via Kakutani's fixed-point theorem, the equilibrium mechanism is left unspecified, and the argument implicitly relies on a hypothetical Walrasian auctioneer to set prices.

Building on the Walrasian model, the Arrow–Debreu model incorporates several extensions intended to provide a more accurate approximation to the real economy. One such extension is the partitioning of the time and space axes into a finite number of segments, which introduces temporal and spatial structures that were absent in the Walrasian model.

In addition, the incorporation of transportation and futures markets allows for intertemporal and interspatial trade, endowing spatial and dynamic structure of the model with substantive meaning.

Compared with the preceding economists, Debreu's approach was mathematically far more advanced and rigorous. To ensure the existence of equilibrium, he imposed several assumptions that were criticized for significantly deviating from reality. Despite such criticisms, he considered a mathematically rigorous approach as effective, as evidenced by the following statement:

The pursuit of generality in a formalized theory is no less imperative than the pursuit of rigor, and the mathematician's compulsive search for ever weaker assumptions is reinforced by the economist's awareness of the limitations of his postulates. (Debreu 1986, p. 1267)

As such, Debreu envisaged the progressive development of mathematical economics as beginning with rigorous analysis under restrictive conditions and then generalizing it by relaxing those conditions. Indeed, the Arrow–Debreu model incorporates elements—including uncertainty, production techniques, interest rates, and temporality—that were absent from the Walrasian model. Although these extensions do not provide an accurate representation of the real economy, they reflect his intention to narrow the gap between model and reality.

Debreu himself rarely mentioned explicit statements regarding the implications of his analysis for the real economy. This may reflect his cautious stance as a mathematician, avoiding discussions—such as model validity or practicality—that are difficult to treat with mathematical rigor. Nevertheless, analytical results derived from the Arrow–Debreu model have been interpreted as providing a theoretical basis for welfare economics and neoliberalism. Against criticisms of unrealistic assumptions, Friedman's instrumentalist view were frequently cited to defend their methodology by arguing that the reality of assumptions is of little importance (Friedman 1953). As a consequence, the general equilibrium model became widely accepted as a mathematical foundation of neoclassical economics and exerted significant influence on policymaking—an outcome that was not necessarily aligned with Debreu's intentions.

3 Comparative Analysis

Marshall once remarked that the greatest difficulty in economic analysis lies in the treatment of time. More than a century has passed since then, yet his observation remains valid today. This section systematically classifies the arguments of earlier proponents from three perspectives: (i) temporal structure, (ii) types of goods, and (iii) concepts of equilibrium. Each of these perspectives is intrinsically related to temporality.

3.1 Temporal Structure

With respect to their temporal structure, the models employed by each proponent can be classified as follows:

- **Continuous-Time Model:**Smith, Mill, Marshall, Samuelson
- **Single-Period Model:**Jevons, Walras ⁹
- **Multi-Period Model:**Debreu

Although continuous-time models provide the most accurate approximation of the real economy, their mathematical analysis is technically demanding. Conversely, single-period models are the least realistic, yet their mathematical analysis is the simplest. Multi-period models fall in between. Therefore, a trade-off arises between reality and mathematical rigor. Depending on whether priority is given to the former or the latter, economists exhibit different tendencies in their treatment of time. Jevons and Walras explicitly acknowledged the static nature of their analyses and prioritized formalization over practicality. By contrast, Marshall remained cautious about the excessive use of mathematics, even though he did not reject its use in economics. Following Mill's approach, he incorporated temporal continuity into his analysis, and emphasized practicality rather than mathematical rigor. Thus, among the marginalist economists, subtle differences can be identified in their attitudes toward the use of mathematics. Yet they shared the common view that mathematical methodologies available in their era were technically limited. None of them considered their formalization of market equilibrium captures market reality in accuracy, as evidenced by numerous caveats in their writings.

The Arrow–Debreu model introduces a dynamic extension to the Walrasian model by assuming a finite time horizon divided into uniformly spaced intervals. However, in comparison with continuous-time models, it still remains an apparent deviation from reality, raising the question of whether it provides a sufficient approximation. Although Debreu's view on the validity of multi-period models is not explicit, his work was undoubtedly influenced by the Hicksian concept of the "week." In *Value and Capital*, Hicks argued that by assuming prices are set only once per week and that firms operate according to plans formulated at the beginning of each week, then persistently evolving economic dynamics can be represented within a discrete-time structure. He also suggested that by assuming firms plan on the basis of well-defined expectations about the future, it makes possible to incorporate intertemporal interactions that are overlooked in static analysis.

I shall define a week as that period of time during which variations in prices can be neglected. For theoretical purposes this means that prices will be supposed to change, not continuously, but at short intervals. [...] We assume that the week is the planning interval—that is to say, all decisions

⁹The analyses of Jevons and Walras are based on static and timeless models. In this respect, their models ought to be called "Timeless Models" instead. Nevertheless, since the subsequent discussion treats single-period and multi-period models within a unified category, the term "Single-Period Model" will be used hereafter for notational convenience.

about the disposition of resources for the future are made on Mondays. Since almost any new decision will involve the making of new contracts, and new contracts can only be made on Mondays, we can very reasonably assume that Mondays are the planning dates too. [...] The plans which are adopted in any given week depend not only upon current prices but also upon the planner's expectations of future prices. We shall generally interpret these expectations in a strict and rigid way, assuming that every individual has a definite idea of what he expects any price which concerns him to be in any future week. [...] These three notions—the week, the plan, the definite expectations—are fundamental for the inquiry which lies before us. By employing them we do a certain amount of violence to the phenomena of the actual world, but not more than seems necessary, if we are to make any headway in dynamic theory. I have tried to show that the rather excessive rigidity of our model need not have very serious consequences. (Hicks 1939, pp. 122–127)

Behind this approach of partitioning the time axis lies Hicks's aim to apply the static analytical framework—originally developed by early contributors such as Jevons and Walras—for practical analysis. However, there is a fundamental difference between multi-period models and continuous-time models. One notable characteristic of exchanges in continuous-time models is that, because entire transactions proceed without interruption, there exist no moment in which all exchanges are completed simultaneously. Multi-period models lack this characteristic. In *Value and Capital*, there is no indication that Hicks considered this issue. Debreu, on the other hand, explicitly states the constraint that agents cannot carry goods into the next period and are effectively enforced to consume all goods in their possession at the end of each period.

The preferences considered here take no account of the resale value of commodities; the i th consumer is interested in these only for the sake of the personal use he is going to make of them. (Debreu 1959, p. 54)

In this respect, multi-period models are no different from single-period models, and the dynamic extension they provide is only partial.

3.2 Type of Goods

We then classify the arguments of past proponents according to the type of goods traded—either commodities or money:¹⁰

- **Money-Mediated Model:**Smith, Marshall, Samuelson
- **Barter Model:**Jevons, Walras, Debreu
- **Both Models are Considered:**Mill

¹⁰In this context, "money" is restricted to an object lacking intrinsic utility. Hence, Walrasian model is excluded from the category of "money-mediated models" despite its treatment of commodity money.

When compared with the previous classification by temporal structure, a consistent pattern can be observed. Both single-period and multi-period models analyze barter exchange, whereas continuous-time models address trade between commodity and money. This tendency arises from the difficulty of incorporating money into single-/multi-period models, in which money cannot play any essential role because all goods are evaluated their utility at the end of each interval. By contrast, continuous-time models allow for the possibility of money's existence, even though they do not themselves explain why money is accepted.

Marshall consistently opposed mathematical analysis based on highly abstract, unrealistic models. He criticized the assumption of barter, arguing that it cannot generate stable prices (Marshall 1920, Appendix F). Other economists who adopted barter models were also not indifferent to this issue. Walras partially incorporated money by introducing a commodity money (or, *numeraire*) with intrinsic value. Furthermore, several studies attempted to introduce money into general equilibrium models.¹¹ Thus, the barter-based approximation was not fully accepted among equilibrium theorists.

The barter-based approximation can be attributed to the influence of Mill's veil of money view, which asserts that money has no substantive effect on the economy. Mill argued that there is no essential difference between barter and money-mediated exchange, and concluded that money is intrinsically insignificant. However, Mill's argument cannot provide theoretical justification for neoclassical economists to rely on barter models because his argument is grounded on the labor theory of value, which had been abandoned by neoclassical economics. In fact, despite being familiar with Mill's work, Jevons did not mention Mill's view. Even so, the use of barter models did not encounter strong opposition, as this view was generally accepted in the economics community at the time, and Jevons explicitly acknowledged that his model does not fully capture the dynamics of real-world exchange. After Jevons, the barter-based approximation has persisted as a convention, while theoretical justification of the use of barter models was rarely clarified. This background calls into question the practical usefulness of results derived from barter-exchange models. This issue is examined critically in the next section.

3.3 Concepts of Equilibrium

Several concepts changed their meaning after the marginal revolution (Table 1). In classical economics (Smith and Mill), demand denotes the "amount of goods desired for purchase," whereas supply represents the "amount of goods for sale"—that is, "actual amount produced." According to these definitions, market equilibrium is a state in which both the demand side and the supply side are able to achieve their desired amounts, provided that the quantity supplied is determined *ex post*. In other words, in an equilibrium state, the demand side can purchase the amount it desires, while the supply side can sell all goods it has produced. In neoclassical economics (Jevons and later), demand is defined in the same way as in classical economics, as the "amount of goods desired for purchase."

¹¹Examples include the model that considers *frictions* in moneyless transactions (Hicks 1989 [1935]) and the one that impose constraints on money balances at the end of each period (Patinkin 1971 [1965]). According to Benetti, however, these efforts cannot readily be considered successful (Benetti 2004).

However, supply is redefined as the "amount of goods desired for sale." In this case, market equilibrium refers to a state in which the demand side can purchase the amount it desires, and the supply side can sell the amount it desires. Thus, classical economics assumes an asymmetry relationship between demand and supply, whereas neoclassical economics treats them symmetrically.

Table 1: Shift in the concepts of equilibrium

	Classical Economics	Neoclassical Economics
Demand	Amount of goods desired for purchase	Amount of goods desired for purchase ¹²
Supply	Amount of goods <i>offered</i> for sale, that is, the quantity actually produced	Amount of goods <i>desired</i> for sale
Equilibrium	The demand side can purchase the desired amount, while the supply side can sell all goods produced ¹³	Both sides can achieve their desired amount

Evidently, the "amount of goods *offered* for sale" is not identical to the "amount of goods *desired* for sale." Mill and Marshall clearly recognized that, in the long run, firms adjust their level of output in accordance with consumer demand. For profit-maximizing firms, the amount they are willing to sell is virtually unlimited. They do not produce the amount they desire simply because some goods would remain unsold. Consequently, classical equilibrium theory should be understood as a theory of disequilibrium according to contemporary definitions. Although market equilibrium theory underwent a substantial transformation at the marginal revolution, this fact has rarely been pointed out.¹⁴

This shift in the definition of supply is closely related to the fact that Jevons and Walras adopted barter exchange models. In a barter exchange, there is no substantive difference between the supply and demand sides, which makes it necessary to define supply, like demand, in terms of the desired amount so as to ensure symmetry between the two. A crucial point is that Marshall also inherited this redefined notion of supply. Unlike Jevons and Walras, his analysis focused on asymmetry markets in which goods are exchanged by money. Accordingly, there was no need for him to adopt the same definition of supply. However, Marshall sought to integrate the two theories of value—the classical labor theory of value, which reflects the firm's perspective, and the neoclassical utility theory of value, which reflects the consumer's perspective. It is likely that he adopted the new definition of supply during this process. The problem here is that, although Marshall and Mill analyzed markets under the same conditions, their results are mutually inconsistent. Mill's argument assumes a disequilibrium market in which firms adjust output in response

¹²Except for Jevons, who did not define demand. The same applies to supply.

¹³Except for Smith, who did not define equilibrium.

¹⁴Such a historical view is inconsistent with the neoclassical assertion that the idea of the "invisible hand" was inherited from Smith and his successors, and was finally resolved by the mathematical analysis of general equilibrium models.

to demand, whereas Marshall’s analysis assumes an equilibrium market in which firms can also achieve the amount they desire to sell. The cause of this inconsistency will be discussed in the next section.

3.4 Two strands in Market Equilibrium Theory

In light of the above discussion, and allowing for several exceptions and deviations, market equilibrium theory can be classified into two strands. One is market equilibrium theory within a static framework, developed by Jevons, Walras, and Debreu. The other is market equilibrium theory within a dynamic framework, developed by Smith, Mill, Marshall, and Samuelson (Table 2). As noted in the previous subsection, dynamic equilibrium theory underwent a transformation around the time of the marginal revolution, which appears in the table as a division within this strand.

Table 2: Strands of Market Equilibrium Theory

	Static	Dynamic	
Temporal Structure	Single-/Multi-period	Continuous-time	
Type of Goods	Barter	Money-mediated	
Assumptions	Hypothetical	Realistic	
Mode of Representation	Mathematical formalization	Natural language (and diagrams)	
Definition of Supply	Amount of goods desired for sale	Amount of goods offered for sale	Amount of goods desired for sale
Equilibrium Condition	Symmetric	Asymmetric	Symmetric
Proponents	Jevons, Walras, Debreu	Smith, Mill	Marshall, Samuelson

Note that the distinction between “static” and “dynamic” used here does not refer to the attainability of equilibrium or the time required for convergence. Rather, it concerns the temporal structure of the model—that is, whether the time horizon is closed or open. In a static framework, a terminal point within a finite interval is presupposed, and utility is evaluated at that point. A dynamic framework, by contrast, posits no such terminal point, thereby allowing goods to be held without consumption for an indefinite duration. Consequently, the concept of utility remains ambiguous.

As discussed in Section 3.1, the advantage of a static framework is that it allows for mathematically rigorous analysis based on utility maximization, although it tends to diverge from the real economy. In contrast, a dynamic framework rests on more realistic assumptions, but is difficult to treat mathematically. This trade-off between mathematical rigor and realism was widely acknowledged by leading marginalists, such as Jevons, Walras, and Marshall. The apparent disagreements over their approaches lie only in which aspect they chose to emphasize as the starting point of analysis. Thus, proponents on both sides must have expected that mathematical rigor and practicality would both be achieved in the

future. The two strands should have been regarded as complementary and held in equal esteem for the development of neoclassical economics.

However, following Debreu's formalization of the general equilibrium model, the interests of mathematical economists were directed toward static equilibrium theory. Although efforts were made to enhance practical relevance by relaxing assumptions while maintaining analytical rigor, it is difficult to argue that this goal has been achieved. As theoretical research on the model accumulated and eventually converged, a broad consensus emerged among economists that the mathematical analysis of market equilibrium theory is largely complete, despite the fact that the implications of general equilibrium theory for practical analysis remain unclear. Conversely, dynamic equilibrium theory has never become a central topic for mathematical economists, and its presence has been limited to the elementary exposition—presumably originating with Samuelson—found in introductory economics textbooks. As a result, a dynamic framework can no longer be called "theory," and is unlikely to be recognized as a research topic. Against this background, an implicit hierarchy may have emerged between the two strands: dynamic equilibrium theory is treated as a subsidiary theory only intended for introductory explanation, whereas static equilibrium theory is regarded as a more fundamental, mathematically sophisticated theory. However, such a hierarchy is nothing more than a consequence of differences in mathematical tractability. The two strands are based on fundamentally distinct temporal structures and should therefore be positioned as independent subjects of theoretical inquiry.

4 Critical Analysis

Section 2 outlined the historical development of market equilibrium theory. The consequent Section 3 showed that the theory can be classified into two main strands—static and dynamic frameworks. Mathematical economists have primarily focused on market equilibrium theory within a static framework. Yet equilibrium theory that rests on a more realistic dynamic framework remains insufficiently analyzed, and the relationship between the two frameworks has not yet been clarified. The following issues remain unresolved.

- The marginal revolution altered the analytical results for money-mediated markets, yielding two mutually contradictory conclusions about the nature of equilibrium.
- Some marginalists adopted the assumption of barter solely for reasons of mathematical tractability, and none of them provided any justification for the claim that the elimination of money has no essential effect on their analysis.
- Multi-period models represent only partial dynamic extensions of single-period models. The extent to which they differ from continuous-time models, as well as their practical usefulness, remains unclear.

This section provides a more detailed and critical examination of these points.

4.1 Logical Flaws in the Money-Mediated Exchange Models

As discussed in Section 3.3, classical and neoclassical economics provide two distinct views concerning the equilibrium state of money-mediated markets. Classical economics presupposes disequilibrium markets in which producers adjust their output level according to consumer demand, whereas neoclassical economics assumes markets to be in equilibrium. The outcome obtained in the DTV paper aligns with the classical view.

Below are the results of a detailed examination of Marshall's and Samuelson's expositions of the price-adjustment mechanism. Each contains logical shortcomings and fails to offer an accurate description of the mechanism.

A Problem in Marshall's Account: Within Marshall's framework, the demand price is defined as the price at which consumers are willing to purchase a given quantity of a commodity and is expressed as a function of the quantity traded. This definition rests on the premise that the demand price is determined solely by the quantity traded. According to Marshall's price-adjustment mechanism, when the demand price exceeds the supply price, producers are able to sell at prices higher than those that justify the current level of sales, leading to an increase in quantity supplied, and *vice versa*. However, his account is problematic because it does not take into consideration the influence of the market price on the demand price. Suppose that a commodity is sold at a certain market price and that a sufficient number of sellers are willing to supply it at that price. In such a case, regardless of the quantity traded, consumers have no reason to pay a price higher than the market price, and the demand price is therefore constrained to be no greater than the market price. To sustain Marshall's argument, the influence of the market price on the demand price must be excluded, which requires evaluating consumers' willingness to purchase under the hypothetical assumption that refusal of exchange entails the immediate loss of the opportunity to purchase the commodity.¹⁵ This assumption holds in single- and multi-period models, in which the exchange value of a commodity is lost once the terminal point of each period is reached. However, because Marshall's equilibrium theory is grounded in a continuous-time framework, the presumption that exchange value is lost at a specific moment is incompatible with the temporal structure of the model.

This issue has likely been dismissed for the following reasons. First, economics at the time

¹⁵Indeed, Marshall appears to have adopted this assumption. In (Marshall 1920), he stated that "The excess of the price which **he would be willing to pay rather than go without the thing**, over that which he actually does pay, is the economic measure of this surplus satisfaction. It may be called *consumer's surplus*." (Italics in original; bold emphasis added by the author). Marshall further argued that the quantity traded is determined at the point where consumer surplus becomes zero. Taken together, his analysis appears to implicitly assume that, once consumers refuse to purchase the commodity at a given price, they cannot purchase the same commodity at a later opportunity. Given the law of one price, one might argue that this constraint is not influential, since waiting for another opportunity would simply result in purchasing at the same price. However, this poses a logical problem when analyzing the optimal pricing strategy of suppliers. This is because, when a single supplier adjusts its price, there is no reason to expect all the other suppliers to do the same. In this respect, the market price as a whole must be distinguished from the price set by any individual supplier.

still retained the characteristics of a moral science, and Marshall himself did not pursue mathematical rigor. Second, Marshall sought to inherit the tradition of classical economics while integrating the new mathematical contributions developed by the marginalists. During that process, it appears that a logical inconsistency emerged when a static notion of utility was incorporated into a dynamic exchange framework. Perhaps, he did not pay sufficient attention to the details of theoretical consistency because his model was largely successful in demonstrating his claim that consumer demand governs prices in the short run while production costs play a more central role in the long run. Finally, Marshall's adoption of a cardinal notion of utility is also relevant, as it encourages an understanding of utility as an intrinsic property of goods, which obscures the influence of external factors such as market prices on the choice of goods.

A Problem in Samuelson's Account: According to Samuelson, price adjustments are driven by inventory levels. When supply exceeds demand at a given price, inventories accumulate, causing prices to fall. By contrast, when demand exceeds supply, inventories are depleted and prices rise under pressure from consumers seeking to obtain commodities. His account, however, contains a logical inconsistency. Inventory changes are determined not by the difference between the amount firms are willing to sell and the amount consumers are willing to purchase; but rather by the difference between the amount firms have produced and the amount consumers have actually purchased. His argument holds only if the amounts desired to sell coincide with the amounts actually produced, yet there is no reason to expect such a condition to be satisfied. Indeed, as noted by Sraffa, firms generally seek to expand their sales volumes and devote significant effort toward this objective (Sraffa 1926, p. 543). It is well known that firms adjust their output levels in accordance with consumer demand, a common business practice that helps to prevent excess inventories from occurring frequently. Even when excess inventories arise, they do not automatically induce price reductions but are typically resolved by curtailing production. Thus, Samuelson's explanation employs the term "supply" in two distinct meanings and mistakenly inherits the classical definition in describing the price-adjustment mechanism.

Samuelson was a leading figure in the mathematization of economics and was highly skilled in mathematical reasoning. Therefore, it appears implausible that such a simple inconsistency would emerge in his own theory. The most reasonable assumption is that he inadvertently introduced a theoretical gap in an attempt to align his exposition with that of Marshall. Another possibility is that, while "demand" commonly refers to the amount desired, "supply" typically carries an ex post connotation, implying the amount actually produced. This encourages conflation of the amount firms are willing to sell with the amount they have actually produced, which may have helped the logical inconsistency remain unnoticed. Finally, since Samuelson's exposition of market equilibrium was presented in an introductory textbook exceeding 600 pages rather than a peer-reviewed article, it is entirely possible that certain theoretical details were not rigorously examined.

4.2 The Rationale for the Barter Model

As discussed in the previous subsection, the neoclassical account of money-mediated markets exhibits several problems. Nevertheless, one might argue that such markets also reach equilibrium by importing analytical results derived from barter models, provided one accepts the veil of money view—that is, the assertion that money has no essential influence on the economy. Since the distinctive nature of money-mediated trading in relation to market equilibrium has rarely been emphasized, it is plausible that this view has been implicitly shared. This line of reasoning, however, is subject to the following counterarguments.

- The fundamental proposition of the veil of money view concerns the invariance of exchange ratios among commodities regardless of the presence of money, rather than the equivalence of market equilibrium states. At least in Mill’s writings, he refers only to exchange ratios, and his account of market adjustment is grounded in disequilibrium rather than equilibrium.
- The plausibility of the veil of money view itself is questionable. Mill maintains that, under a capitalist system, relative prices are determined by production cost ratios irrespective of the presence of money. However, it is difficult to conceive of such a system operating within a barter economy, for the ultimate purpose of capitalism lies in the reproduction of capital in monetary form. Moreover, contemporary mathematical economics still faces substantial difficulties in its treatment of money, and therefore often relies on highly stylized approximations. On this basis, it is difficult to maintain that the presence of money is irrelevant within the contemporary framework.
- As shown in the DTV paper, once the temporal continuity of exchanges is taken into account, agents must always consider the exchangeability of goods when making choices. Therefore, the influence of surrounding environments, including market institutions, on preferences over goods is no longer negligible. It is thus unlikely that exchange ratios are preserved across two distinct institutional arrangements, namely a barter economy and a monetary economy.

Given the above discussion, the veil of money view does not adequately address the issue raised in the previous section. We therefore conclude that the arguments of the preceding proponents provide no theoretical basis for the attainment of equilibrium in money-mediated markets.

4.3 A Problem with Multi-Period Models

At the time of the marginal revolution, mathematical methods based on the assumption of utility-maximization were largely restricted to static models, and even their founders left numerous notes and caveats about their practical applicability. After the proposal of the Hicksian “week”, however, marginal utility theory was considered applicable to dynamic models as well, as evidenced by its broad application to various dynamic formulations, including Arrow–Debreu general equilibrium models. Together with its resemblance to

the formalization found in the natural sciences, this development fostered the impression that mathematical economics based on rational individuals had reached an adequate level for practical purposes, including policymaking.

Given that methodologies which discretize the time and space into finite segments are also common in numerical simulations in physics (e.g., the finite element method in solid mechanics), the "week" concept may seem to raise no methodological concerns. However, this approach has the following theoretical shortcomings.

- In industrial applications, it is expected that discrete models will closely approximate their continuous counterparts. This implies that as the segment size approaches zero, the discrepancy from the continuous model should likewise vanish. In Arrow–Debreu models, however, shortening the interval tends to generate substantial volatility in exchange ratios, due to the increased dispersion of initial endowments across periods.
- Arrow–Debreu models assume a hypothetical time-space structure with artificial boundaries, within which the carryover or transfer of goods is restricted except through markets. Under such conditions, infinitesimal segmentation effectively eliminates the mobility of goods at every point in time, thereby making the possession of goods impossible.

Consequently, a continuous-time model cannot be adequately approximated by discretizing the time axis into "weekly" intervals and analyzing each interval as a static utility-maximization problem.¹⁶ To the best of the author's knowledge, the perspective discussed above has not been addressed in Hicks (Hicks 1939) or in the subsequent literature. It appears that such an issue has largely gone unnoticed.¹⁷

5 Conclusion

The outcome of our historical investigation is consistent with that of the DTV paper. The neoclassical account of money-mediated markets, according to which supply and demand reach equilibrium as in barter markets, exhibits a clear logical inconsistency. No valid foundation can be found in the arguments of leading proponents for the claim that a money-mediated economy can be reduced to a barter economy. Furthermore, classical economics presupposes disequilibrium markets in which producers adjust their output levels in accordance with consumer demand.

The central claim of this paper challenges one of the most fundamental beliefs in neoclassical economics. Given that neoclassical economics has placed greater emphasis on mathematical rigor than any other school of thought, the idea that such a fundamental flaw

¹⁶From a similar perspective, the DTV paper offers a more detailed critique.

¹⁷One reason that hinders recognition of this issue is that representative DSGE models incorporate intertemporal utility-maximization problems, such as the Ramsey model and the Euler equation. These models implicitly suggest that intertemporal ownership of goods is properly considered in the neoclassical framework. In reality, however, these considerations of intertemporal ownership are merely partial and are not applied to market equilibrium theory, which results in an internal inconsistency within these models.

exists at its theoretical core will likely be unacceptable not only to economists but also to non-specialists. One reason this issue has been overlooked may lie in the structure of contemporary economics education. In the early stage of the curricula, students learn the mechanism of market equilibrium originally presented by Samuelson. At this stage, the explanation is simplified for introductory purposes, and students are generally expected to accept it without critical scrutiny. At later stages, students study more advanced and rigorous market theory, which typically treats barter exchange in static models (single-/multi-period models). By mastering these analyses, students come to hold the mistaken belief that the same results can be applied to the Samuelson's market model that they encountered in their introductory courses. However, as demonstrated in the DTV paper, there is a substantial difference between dynamic models with open time horizon and static models with closed time horizon. It is therefore inappropriate to apply the mathematical analysis of the latter to the former. In a more realistic analysis that incorporates money, markets must be understood as reaching a "disequilibrium" state in which prices are determined and equilibrate at a point away from the intersection, as suggested by classical economics and the DTV paper. The problem found in typical textbook expositions ultimately originates from the neoclassical value theory, which relies on a static notion of utility. This point further substantiates the DTV paper's call for a dynamic treatment of value.

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